

Cow urine based dermal defender: A review

G Karpagam , K Pavithra , S Kowsalya ,R Devadharshini , P Mohana priya and A M Ramachandran *

Department of Microbiology, Dr. N.G.P Arts and Science College, Coimbatore, India.

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Abstract

It is indispensable to maintain a healthy skin from infectious microorganisms like Bacteria, Fungi, viruses and parasites. Most common biological agents Bacteria and Fungi plays a prominent role in worsening the skin infections. Antimicrobial and antifungal studies of various natural (herbal extracts) and synthetic compounds are still going on to find out the best results against skin infection causing microbes. For the treatment of skin infections: soaps, creams, ointments and skin care lotions containing chemicals are available but due to certain limitations the people are frequently attracted towards herbal formulative products. Cow urine is profound to have a great therapeutic value. Across many parts of the world, cow urine therapy is highly used and recommended by medicinal practitioners. Cow urine remove dark circles, black spots and pimples says Gujarat government's Gauseva and Gauchar Vikas Board. Due to cow urine's great impact, even branded cosmetic companies started formulating cosmetic commercial products using the cow urine as a constituent in skin care products. Since, numerous researches experimentally proved that cow urine acts as a wide defender of skin.

Keywords: Cow urine; Skin infection; Distillate; Photoactivated; Antimicrobial; Skin care; Cosmetics

1. Introduction

Dermal infections are common among all age groups. It occurs when skin is exposed towards microbes, chemical agents and to some extent it may be also due to malnutrition [1]. Bacterial and fungal infections are highly contagious and spread easily from infected person through close contact or sharing a comb or hairbrush [2], Atopic dermatitis is the chronic condition that causes restless, inflamed skin. If the skin infections remain ignored, it can spread from skin to blood stream. From ancient period, herbs are used for maintenance of skin care and beauty. It has been witnessed that there is a relationship between the beauty and cosmetics [3]. In day to day life, disinfectants like soaps and detergents are useful in hygienic practices to remove dirt, dust, microbes and bad odor from the skin to maintain health and beauty [4]. Still there is an outstanding research are going on medicinal plants because of their less side effects in drugs.

Medicinal plants have imminent health benefits due to the presence of active ingredients present in them which have been widely used to formulate soaps, creams, oils and ointments for treating skin related ailments like acne, ringworm, wound and other skin infections. Nowadays, most of the consumers are strongly refusing the synthetic chemicals in cosmetic products. As there is an increasing demand for natural ingredients containing cosmetic products [5]. For example, An oldest cosmetic product is soap. 65% to 85% of bacteria from human skin can be removed with a good antibacterial soap [6]. Topical Creams and ointments both has a significant role in cosmetics and medicines in skin care. Apart from emollients as ingredients in skin care products, cow urine is also used as an important ingredient in cosmetics

In this hustle and bustle emergency medical era, 70% of pathogenic bacteria are resistant to at least one of the drugs. Attention to effective drugs are hiring to find the better alternative drugs. Ancient and Indian Literature states that Cow

* Corresponding author: A. M. Ramachandran

urine (Sanskrit : Gomutra) has great pharmacological importance. Cow urine is said to be a panacea of all diseases [7]. Some people recognize cow urine as “ water of Life”. Though urine of several domestic animals is of therapeutic value in unani medicine, cow’s urine is described as the best compared to others [8]. Cow urine therapy was not only used in India, but all around globally for several centuries. In addition to this, cow urine is also used as a natural disinfectant in rural villages.

2. Skin Infections

Skin is the largest organ in the body [9]. Each and every individuals skin is different. It is important to acquire the knowledge regarding the skin type and skin infections. There are five different types of healthy skin: Normal, dry, oily, combination (both oily and dry skin) and sensitive. In fact, every individual experiences any sort of skin infection in the lifetime. Skin infections may be either primary or secondary. Bacteria are the most significant culprit for causing various skin infections.

2.1. Bacterial skin infections

Bacterial skin infections are the 28th most commonly diagnosed skin infections in the hospitalized patients [10]. Most of the nosocomial skin infections are caused by bacteria. This kind of skin infection initiate as small, red bumps that gradually get increase in size. It ranges from mild to severe conditions. Some can be easily treated with topical ointments but some requires oral antibiotic. Various types of bacterial skin infections shows in Table 1

Table 1 Type Of Bacterial Skin Infection And Its Causative Organism

S.No	Type of bacterial skin infection	Causative organism
1	Cellulitis	<i>Staphylococcus and Streptococcus</i>
2	Erysipelas	<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>
3	Impetigo	<i>Staphylococcus aureus and Streptococcus pyogenes</i>
4	Ecthyma	<i>Beta - hemolytic streptococci</i>
5	Abscess	<i>Staphylococci</i>
6	Folliculitis	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>

2.2. Viral skin infections

Virus is responsible for this kind of infection. This also ranges from mild to severe. Different types of viral infections include: Measles, chickenpox, herpes zoster and Molluscum contagiosum. In a study of skin diseases, 145 organ transplanted children are infected with Molluscum contagiosum [11].

2.3. Fungal skin infections

Fungus is responsible for causing fungal skin infection. In this new millennium, there is a drastical increase of fungal infections in various ecosystems [12]. Mostly it develops in the wet and damp areas of the skin such as armpit or feet. They are contagious and non-life threatening. Dermatophytosis caused by dermatophytes penetrate the stratum corneum skin layer by producing long hyphal chains [13]. By undertaking proper medications they can be controlled in their initial stage. Different types of fungal infections include: Ringworm, yeast infection, nail fungus, oral thrush.

2.4. Parasitic skin infections

Parasitic skin infections are caused by parasites. These kind of infections even spread beyond the skin to the bloodstream and organs. Though non-life threatening, It cause an uncomfortable mode throughout its presence. Some of the parasitic infections include: scabies, lice. The most commonest parasitic skin infection scabies is contagious which can be transmitted through personal contact and transmission through fomite is rare [14,15].

3. Cow Urine: A Momentous Gift For Skin Care

In Rigveda, cow's urine is compared to nectar. Cow urine has certain volatile and non-volatile components which might have high Antimicrobial [16] and Anthelmintic activity. Cow urine has also been granted US patents (US Patent No. 6896907,6410059) for its active role as an antibiotic, antifungal and anticancer agent [17]. Cow urine is useful in treating number of diseases like Fever, epilepsy, anemia, abdominal pain, constipation [18] shows in Fig 1. It has immunomodulatory [21], hypoglycemic [22] and cardio-respiratory effects [23]. In ayurvedic pharmaceuticals, cow urine also enhance the properties of many drugs by undergoing repeated trituration. Cow urine prevents the cells from free radicles which damage the healthy cells and induce tumor cells. Cow urine has been used to strengthen the effects of medicinal herbs says "Shan Han Lun " a Chinese pharmaceutical dictionary [24].

Figure 1 Diseases cured by Cow urine along with subsidiaries [19,20]

3.1. Chemical Composition of Cow urine

The ingredients and percentage of constituents present in the cow urine [25] shows in Table 2. Several researches states that cow urine contains nitrogen, sulphur, phosphate, sodium, manganese, carbolic acid, iron, silicon, chlorine, magnesium, citric, titric, succinic, calcium salts, Vitamins A, B, C, D and E, Minerals, lactose, enzymes, creatinine, hormones, urea and gold acids. Urea is the key chemical in urine, this is the principle behind cow urine being effective fungicide as well as antibacterial agent [26,27]. Cow urine increases the secretion of interleukin-1 and interleukin-2 [28]. Early morning first voided cow urine is more sterile and effective as it contains more macro and micronutrients along with other enzymes [29]. Cow urine contains some of the important components such as pheromones [30], urinary proteins [31], Calcium [32], Estrogen [33].

Table 2 Chemical Composition Of Cow Urine

S. No	Name of the ingredient	Percentage
1.	Water	95%
2.	Urea	2.5%
3.	Minerals, Salts, Hormones and enzymes	2.5%
4.	Ammonium nitrogen	1-1.7ml/kg/day
5.	Calcium	0.1-1.4ml/kg/day
6.	Chloride	0.1-1.1mmol/kg/day
7.	Creatinine	15-20mg/kg/day
8.	Potassium	0.08-0.15mmol/kg/day
9.	Uric acid	1-4mg/kg/day
10.	Allantoin	20- 60ml/kg/day

3.2. Different forms of Cow Urine

There are three different forms of Cow urine. They are

- Fresh Cow urine
- Photoactivated cow urine
- Cow urine distillate

Thus each form of cow urine has its own different benefits.

4. Effective Properties of Cow Urine

4.1. Antibacterial

Cow urine exhibits antibacterial activity against major skin infectious microbes like *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus vulgaris* and *Enterobacter aerogenes* using Disc diffusion method. It is found that cow urine extract of *Azadiractica indica* beneficial in multidrug resistance treatment against *E.coli* and *Klebseilla pneumonia*. Cefixime was used as standard [34,35]. It was confirmed that Cow urine exhibits both the antioxidant and antimicrobial activities [36]. Fresh cow urine has better antibacterial property than compared to its distillate [37].

4.2. Antifungal

Antifungal activity of cow urine distillate was analysed against *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavus* and comparison showed maximum growth suppression in *Aspergillus niger* (3 ± 0.14 , 6.3 ± 1.2 and 7.06 ± 0.04 , mm in diameter) than *Aspergillus flavus* (2.03 ± 0.25 , 4.9 ± 0.26 and 6.3 ± 1.2 , mm in diameter, respectively) [38,39]. Inhibition of fungal growth was carried out by comparing the cow urine samples of outdoor and indoor breeding cows. Ultimately, outdoor cow urine inhibited more fungal growth compared to the indoor breeding cow urine [40]. Cow urine inhibits the growth of *Malassezia* a dandruff causing fungi [41].

4.3. Antioxidant

Compared to residue, distillate and re-distillate of cow urine antioxidant activity seen highly in fresh cow urine [42]. It was observed experimentally that DPPH radial scavenging activity and superoxide scavenging activity of cow urine and its distillate inhibited the free radicals. Fresh cow urine seems more active than its distillate in inhibiting the free radicals [43]. Cow urine prevents the cells from free radicles which damage the healthy cells and induce tumor cells.

4.4. Antihelmintic

Helminthes are the main reason for affecting livestock production in tropical areas. It cause chronic diseases in nature [44]. Cow urine concentrate against adult earthworm *Pheretima pashuma* was performed and cow urine concentrate at dose dependent level caused paralysis and death of worms [45].

4.5. Anticancer

Cow urine inhibits the apoptosis of lymphocytes and repair the damaged DNA. It is more effectively used in anticancer therapy [46]. It has been reported that the Re-distillate cow urine acts as an anticancer agent where Amrutha sara made from cow urine made the patient completely recovered from oropharyngeal carcinoma [47].

4.6. Antiseptic

On experimental observations, Cow urine showed the extraordinary wound healing activity [48]. Allantoin is one active constituent present in cow urine. It helps in the regeneration of damaged epithelial cell and helps in enhancement of epithelial cells followed by wound healing activity. Allantoin neutralizes the irritating and sensitizing agents by act as an anti-irritant [49]. Thus cow urine has many positive effects due to certain substances present in it and exhibit various medicinal properties shows in Fig 2 and 3.

Figure 2 Medicinal properties of Cow Urine

Antimicrobial and Germicidal	•Urea, creatinine, carbolic acid, phenols, calcium and manganese
Antifungal	•Phenolic acids – Gallic, caffeic, ferulic, o-coumaric, cinnamic and salicylic acids.
Antibacterial	• Amino acids and urinary peptides

Figure 3 Substances present in the cow urine and its positive effect

5. Cosmetic Products Made Of Cow Urine

Table 3 Different Cosmetic products made of Cow urine

Cosmetics made of Cow urine	Reference
Face wash	51
Soap	52
Face pack	52
Anti lice shampoo	-
Hair conditioner	53
Antidandruff shampoo	-
Ointment	54
Acne cream	-
Hair tonic	55
Hair fall control	-

Cow urine purifies the blood and treats any kind of skin infections. Microbial Skin infections occurs due to the toxic compounds released by microbes in the skin. Cow urine is used in skin care products to enhance the effectiveness in formulating products to protect the skin. It is used as one of the major ingredients in some of the cosmetic products [50]. Table 3 shows the list of cosmetic products made of cow urine.

Apart from cosmetics cow urine is also incorporated in,

- Anti-aging cream
- Anti-wrinkle cream
- Toothpaste
- Mouthwash

6. Conclusion

Hence, it is evidently acknowledged that cow urine acts as a defender for skin in treating skin infections. From the old golden traditional days, cow urine is used in all sorts of skin infections in many formulations. This created a great impact of cow urine in this modern era. Thus it has been proved that it has enormous properties being an easily available one in nature. Its effective ingredients makes it more content in making medicines and cosmetics. It is not only useful in skin care but also very beneficial in hair care. It also act as a bio enhancer by having Antibacterial, Antifungal & Antioxidant properties. Thus, from the literary works it's strongly agreed that cow urine act as a potential agent against skin diseases. Cow urine would be more efficacious in curing skin related infections of its used in proper concentration.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest.

Author's contribution

Karpagam G, Pavithra K, Kowsalya S, Devadharshni R, Mohana priya P and Ramachandran A.M. contributed to the paper's development.

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